

IMPACT OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY IN INDIA

by

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India has long been a fairly traditional society, with informal means of control that have proven to be effective in regulating the behaviour of people of all ages, castes, sexes, and other typological groups. Customs, traditions, morals, values, and norms formed and adhered to locally as well as generally in Indian society by people of all groups and locales have all contributed to low crime and delinquency rates for generations. As a social control agent, religion played a critical role. Until British dominance in India, there were no institutional laws and regulations, police, or courts. However, throughout generations and centuries, the type of informal surveillance system that was built and maintained benefited society well. The legal system at the communal level aided in the regulation of human behaviour and the maintenance of order. Industrialization, urbanisation, modernization, population increase, depleting natural resources, and other factors have all contributed to a new situation in which some groups have been deprived of basic facilities to settle down and enjoy improved living conditions. This prompted them to express themselves by departing from the accepted informal standards of behaviour that had formed in recent years. Intercultural, social, economic, religious, and political diversity in various locations hampered the development of a uniform code of conduct for people to follow in various social contexts. As a result, there are no defined standards of behaviour established by the state or society, and they are consequently violated by one or more groups for various reasons. Like crime, juvenile delinquency is socially defined and culturally perceived. Politically sanctioned and economically measurable This is in the sense that it is unique. While it is being empirically researched, several aspects of it must be considered. We're attempting to figure out what's going on at the national level. In terms of human behaviour, this has happened and continues to happen. Particularly with minors under the age of 18 who are involved in legal as well as illegal activities. Children or juveniles are societal factors. They are supposed to be under the strict control of their parents, relatives, neighbourhood, community, and so on as children, but when circumstances encourage and warrant it, they turn to violating the community or society's standards of behaviour, leading to them being labelled as juvenile delinquents within legal frameworks. Only those youngsters who are considered delinquents according to legal norms are considered in this study. Many of their delinquent behaviour may not have been brought under the legal restrictions and recorded by the state's authority or authorities, either purposefully or accidentally. There could be a lot of violations of behaviour rules carried out by youngsters in villages and other unnoticed locations that go unnoticed. As a result, the facts and

numbers obtained from the state's records are important. Although restricted, agencies do provide a foundation for our understanding of the world. Nature, extent, and fluctuations in a changing residential and regional environment and sub-regional circumstances In this investigation, an attempt is made to take into account taking into account the statistical data collected by state agencies on the children's criminal acts, which provide as a foundation for understanding the In contemporary culture, there are tendencies and patterns of delinquent behaviour.

But this Juvenile Delinquency issue is no less worrying for India even, as can be clearly seen from the below statistics published by the National Crime Records Bureau in India in 2016

The problem of juvenile delinquency in a developing country like India is considered low when compared to other developed countries like the United States, but what is concerning is the steadily increasing juvenile delinquency problem in India in recent years, as evidenced by data published by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) every year. When we compare India's statistics to those of the United States, we find the following:

Juvenile delinquency is a serious problem in the United States, with 45,567 minors detained in juvenile detention centres in 2016. In reality, about one-fifth of all people arrested in the United States are under the age of eighteen.¹

However, as the following figures from India's National Crime Records Bureau show, the issue of juvenile delinquency is no less concerning for the country.²

In States and UTs, 'Juveniles in Conflict with the Law'

a) The highest number of juveniles in conflict with the law cases were reported in Madhya Pradesh (20.6%) (7,369 cases), Maharashtra (18.4% (6,606 cases), and Delhi UT (7.0%) (2,499 instances) in 2016.

b) During 2016, 44,171 juveniles were apprehended in 35,849 cases, with 41,826 juveniles being apprehended under the IPC and 2,345 juveniles being apprehended under the SLL.

c) During 2016, the majority of minors in confrontation with the law caught under the IPC and SLL offences (73.8 percent) (32,577 out of 44,171) were between the ages of 16 and 18.

'Juveniles in Conflict with the Law' in Metropolitan Cities (i.e. 19 Indian cities with populations exceeding 2 million)

¹ Prino, C.T. & Peyrot, M. (1994) The Effect of Child Physical Abuse and Neglect on Aggressive with Drawn and Prosocial Behaviour. *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 18(10), 871-884.

² <http://ncrb.gov.in/StatPublications/CII/CII2016/pdfs/NEWPDFs/Crime%20in%20India%20-%202016%20Complete%20PDF%20291117.pdf>

a) In 2016, the cities with the highest number of incidents involving juveniles in conflict with the law were Delhi (35.6%), Mumbai (14.2%), and Pune (11.3%).

b) During 2016, a total of 9,341 juveniles were apprehended in 6,645 cases, including 8,971 juveniles apprehended under the IPC and 370 juveniles apprehended under the SLL.

c) During 2016, the majority of adolescents in confrontation with the law caught under the IPC and SLL offences (73.7 percent) (6,881 out of 9,341) were between the ages of 16 and 18.

The increased engagement of adolescents in horrific crimes like rape presently in India, as compared to the petty crimes they were involved in previously, is a highly alarming trend that has been detected based on the NCRB reports data analysis. While there has been a continuous increase in small crimes such as stealing committed by adolescents in recent years, there has also been an exponential growth in terrible 143 crimes such as rape and murder, which is extremely distressing. In India, for example, according to the NCRB report, there were 855 adolescents charged with murder in 2016, up from 465 in 2003.

According to the 2013 NCRB data, there were 466 rape cases recorded against minors across the country in 2003, but there were 1737 rape cases registered against juveniles in 2013, a dramatic increase in a decade. The above steadily increasing volume of juvenile crimes in recent years clearly illustrates the growing severity of the country's juvenile delinquency problem, and thus its overall influence is not restricted to the afflicted youngster and his family, but rather extends to a wide range of other sections.

Not only does juvenile delinquency have an influence on the victims of crime, but it also has an impact on the delinquent's family, future, and society as a whole, and its impact on different parts can be explained.

Victims' Experiences

Victims are the most visible people harmed by juvenile delinquency. The victim always loses, whether the offence is theft, vandalism, or assault. In addition to the cost of replacing damaged or destroyed things, the victim may face expenses such as missed wages, medical care, or psychological counselling.

The Impact on Juvenile Delinquents

When a child commits a crime, he or she is likely to experience unanticipated consequences. He or she may lose his or her liberty while incarcerated or on probation. Academically, the adolescent may fall behind. Although incarceration in a juvenile detention centre may be an acceptable punishment for the adolescent's illegal behaviour, it also places him or her in contact with other delinquents, some of whom may be more clever or influential. This increases the likelihood of recidivism, and in many places, if a juvenile beyond the age of 14 commits a

second offence, he or she might be prosecuted and sentenced as an adult. The misbehaviour of the adolescent may have long-term consequences for his or her college and professional choices.

Families' Consequences

The upheaval and trauma of having a family member who is a juvenile delinquent might cause other relatives to become unstable. Not only must the family deal with the requirements of the troubled child, but they may also be forced to gather enormous sums of money to pay for lawyers. In addition, the family must deal with ethical considerations surrounding the child's obligation to the victims of his crime. Families are typically required to attend group counselling sessions, which can be inconvenient and costly while the child is in prison or on probation.

Community Consequences

Juvenile delinquency has been linked to drug use, gang activity, alcohol misuse, and sexual behaviour. By making neighbourhoods dangerous and requiring significant sums of public funds to be spent on law enforcement and school safety, communities suffer.

The Impact on Society

Young people who commit serious crimes before they turn 18 are a danger to everyone involved. They may be behaving out in response to imagined wrongdoings committed against them. They may believe that there is no way out of a life of crime for them. They could be expressing rage or displeasure at another person or group, or they could be looking for gang acceptance. Juvenile misbehaviour impacts far too many Indian individuals, families, and communities, regardless of the motivation. It's a significant issue that government agencies, legislators, educators, faith communities, and charitable organisations are all working to address.

Finally, because each of the aforementioned societal entities is a vital component, This juvenile delinquency problem has an influence on our nation as a whole. Overall progress of our country, as well as raises concerns about our country's future. This country is now in the hands of today's children.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this chapter is that there is no one reason or clear solution. An explanation for the emergence of delinquent behaviour in youngsters is presented. Though the reasons of adolescent misbehaviour in India are comparable to those in the United States, observed on a worldwide scale, but due to the country's diversity, it varies slightly across the country. Due to the fact that India is a fast-paced civilization, its culture and traditional framework have been preserved.

A growing country with quickly changing norms, values, and other factors. As previously stated, the causes of juvenile delinquency are diverse, ranging from bad company, adolescent instability

and impulses, early sex experience, mental conflicts, extreme social suggestibility, love of adventure, motion picture, school dissatisfaction, poor recreation, street life, vocational dissatisfaction, sudden impulse, and various physical conditions.

The elements that contribute to juvenile delinquency can be divided into two categories: (a) social influences and (b) personal factors. Broken households, poverty, delinquent area associates and gangs, beggary, school learning discontent, films and pornographic literature, and deep buried inner cravings are some of the socioeconomic elements that contribute to adolescent delinquency. Mental deficit, emotional issues, and other personal or individual variables contribute to delinquency in youth. As a result, we can deduce that a delinquent child's psyche is caused by a variety of factors. The rising prevalence of juvenile delinquency in India is having an influence on several segments of society, not just the victim or juvenile delinquent himself, which, in turn, has an impact on the nation's overall growth, as seen in the above analysis. As a result, if we want to properly control and eradicate this problem from our country, we need to take a close look at it and take collective action from diverse segments of society.

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